

PRINCIPLES OF DEVELOPMENT OF THE FINANCIAL MANAGEMENT SYSTEM IN UZBEKISTAN

Qudbiyev Nodir Tohirovich

Fergana polytechnic institute,
Assistant, Department of Accounting and Audit,
e-mail: nodir.qudbiyev@ferpi.uz, +998911054548
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10605170>

ARTICLE INFO

Qabul qilindi: 25-January 2024 yil
Ma'qullandi: 28- January 2024 yil
Nashr qilindi: 31- January 2024 yil

KEY WORDS

accounting (financial) reporting, enterprise management, financial analysis, financial management, financial indicators, financial resources

ABSTRACT

This article will consider the features and principles of the development of the financial management system in Uzbekistan. At the current stage of cardinal reforms being carried out in the economy of our republic, special attention is being paid to the development of the digital economy. The gradual development of the financial management mechanism in business entities based on digital financial technologies is closely linked to international integration, which, in turn, leads to the emphasis on solving issues such as improving modern management processes, selling to foreign investors based on reducing the state's share in large joint-stock companies.

Introduction. In the context of diversification and structural changes in the sectors of the economy, the development of financial activities of corporate structures, it becomes urgent to further enhance the role and importance of financial management in ensuring financial stability. The introduction of modern corporate governance methods at enterprises (joint-stock companies) operating in our republic, in particular, the study of the theoretical and economic foundations of financial management, the development of knowledge aimed at improving the mechanism of financial management, the rational use of best practices of foreign statehood in the field of science are considered important.

It should be noted that in the context of the development of market relations, special attention is paid to a new approach to the financial management system of joint-stock companies. The management of an enterprise depends on a number of factors, such as the availability of economically independent and financially stable types of activities, the correct organization of management in them, the rational organization of production and service with effective use of existing opportunities, the use of scientific and technical innovations, new information technologies, the correct organization of financial management work.

Any enterprise, as a result of its activities, makes certain decisions and carries out certain business operations. Almost every such decision or business transaction is reflected in accounting. In this regard, it is impossible to manage an enterprise without information about its activities in terms of all its aspects. Management is based on activity analysis data, which,

in turn, is based on accounting (financial) reporting data. By “reading” the reports, the analyst, the head can learn a lot of interesting and useful information, which is the basis for making various management decisions in the future. However, it is important to remember that the reports submitted for analysis must be reliable.

For effective management of business structures, it is important that managers have access to the necessary information and are able to use it. This information should be processed accordingly, draw the right conclusions and use them to make management decisions to improve production efficiency.

Every employee engaged in the analysis of financial and economic activities of an enterprise, as well as using accounting data, should be able to read and analyze the balance sheet and other forms, understand their articles, have economic categories and indicators characterizing them, as well as give effective conclusions and recommendations for making managerial decisions.

After the Republic of Uzbekistan gained independence, the priority task was to create the legal and organizational foundations for the formation of a multi-level economy and a competitive environment capable of ensuring high rates of economic growth and sustainable development of society. The experience of reforming transition economies shows that the most important means of a harmonious transition from an administratively planned economy to a market model of management are privatization and axonerization, which leads to the formation of a real class of owners, and financial management acquires special importance when introducing effective methods of corporate management of privatized property.

As a result of economic reforms in Uzbekistan, structural transformations of enterprises are being carried out and modern management methods are being introduced into their activities. However, in modern conditions, the level of ensuring the functioning of modern management mechanisms at enterprises based on the use of innovative ideas and technological developments, improving management efficiency and effective use of investments remains low. Therefore, the new development strategy of Uzbekistan for 2022-2026 defines such priority tasks as “accelerated development of the national economy and ensuring high growth rates”, the fulfillment of this task requires increasing the efficiency of using modern management methods in managing the activities of enterprises.

Research methodology. When writing the article, an assessment of the current state of the features and principles of the development of the financial management system in Uzbekistan was carried out using the expert assessment method and determining areas of improvement. The expert assessment method is a set of logical and mathematical-statistical methods and procedures aimed at obtaining the necessary information for the preparation and selection of rational solutions to a certain range of issues.

Literature review. Economic scientists express different opinions when explaining the economic content of financial management in international and national practice. Of course, we can see that the opinions expressed in some cases differ in their approach to this concept, in addition to explaining the essence of financial management. The main reason for this, and before studying the opinions of scientists, it is worth focusing on international approaches to the concept of financial management and on various aspects in it.

The authors of numerous scientific literature devoted to the coverage of the economic content and practical aspects of financial management are American economic scientists

James Van Ham and John Wachowicz (James C. Van Horne, John M. Wachowicz), who describe financial management as follows. Financial Management is the process of formation, financing and asset management, which implies the achievement of several main goals. Accordingly, in financial management, the decision-making function will focus on the following three main areas: investment, financing and asset management decision-making. According to scientists, financial managers, in exchange for effective formation, financing and rational management of financial assets, contribute not only to ensuring the financial stability of the company in the future, but also to ensuring economic progress. Despite the fact that the goals of firms and companies are different, the main one is to maximize the financial condition of the owners (owners) of the company.

Well-known American economists Stephen A. Ross (Stephen A. Ross), who conducted many studies on the science of financial management, Randolph Westerfield (Randolph W. Westerfield) and Bradford D. Jordan believe that financial managers should take responsibility in three main areas of a company's business. The first is financing (budgeting) of capital investments, that is, planning and managing long-term capital investments of the company]. The second is the structural structure of the company's capital, that is, determining and managing the necessary sources of supply to finance the company's long-term capital investments. The third is working capital, that is, the management of short-term assets and liabilities in order to ensure the regularity of the company's activities and the continuity of the production process.

L. Fung, Professor at Birkbeck University (Birkbeck — University of London) in the UK, believes that "financial management refers to the decision-making process related to the control and financial planning of company subsystems, which includes treasury; assessment, selection, control and management of new investment opportunities; ensuring and managing growth dynamics long-term financial assets; financial risk management; management of short-term and long-term financial activities of the company".

The Russian academic economist, headed by G.B. Polsky, noted that the concept of financial management as an active component of an economic mechanism is related to the concepts of a financial management mechanism of enterprises or a financial mechanism. Financial management is the process of formation and rational use of financial resources in enterprises, working capital management. Financial management is a generalized system of methods, applications and levers used in the process of managing financial resources and working capital at enterprises.

It should be noted that in subsequent years, scientific, theoretical and practical research on the organization of the financial management system in our country has been conducted on a large scale. In turn, the concept of financial management is also defined by economic scientists of our country.

In particular, Professor O.K. Iminov believes that "financial management is a system of principles and methods for the development and implementation of management decisions in the organization of the circulation of monetary resources of an enterprise and in the process of maintenance, distribution, and use of financial resources".

B. Tashmurodova, S. Elmirzaev and N. In Tursunova's textbook "Financial Management", this concept is described as follows: "Financial management is the management of financial resources and financial activities aimed at the implementation of strategic and current goals

of the enterprise".

R.Karlibaeva expressed the following opinion in her research work, based on various approaches to the definition of financial management. As a result of the study of financial management as a special field of science and practice, the following conclusions were formulated: first of all, financial management is a synthesis of management theory, financial theory and analytical accounting apparatus; Secondly, financial management is a multidimensional concept that can be considered, on the one hand, as a science, and on the other hand, as a separate type of independent practical activity in the company's management system, combining a specific subject, an object and an arsenal of management tools; in particular Thirdly, the main function of financial management is the process of making optimal decisions.

Based on the definitions given by the above—mentioned scientists, the concept of financial management can be described as follows: financial management - the development and implementation of current and strategic goals of an enterprise, the implementation of functions such as forecasting the financial situation in the future, management and assessment of financial risks, planning, management processes of effective formation and rational use of financial resources.

Analysis and results. In our opinion, financial management is the science and art of managing the cash flows of joint-stock companies, attracting the most rational sources of financial resources and using them with the greatest efficiency to achieve the strategic and tactical goals of joint-stock companies.

The content of financial management is a much broader concept than its essence. In a market economy, the law of value plays a regulatory role, and financial relations cover the entire production process in joint-stock companies, including all economic relations. Thus, financial management is the main component of the general management system of a joint-stock company. Financial management - profit maximization is the goal of the entire management system at the same time, including technical and production management.

The process of making financial decisions, as well as making any management decisions, will consist of three stages.

Each type of solution requires specific information and analytical support. Forecasting and planning decisions are based on a generalized accounting report for a number of years or quarters using promising trend analysis methods. Decisions regulating the course of economic activity are based on operational, including accounting information, using operational analysis methods. Assessment and control decisions are based on retrospection, support for current analysis methods, and comparison of current and planned (forecast) data for the current reporting period.

The content of modern financial management is characterized by the deepening of financial analysis methods and the solution of new problems associated with the transition of the Republic of Uzbekistan to market conditions. Such problems include, for example, discounting income and capital, managing the capital structure by determining the cost of capital, the ability to use economic diagnostic methods, financial risk management, the effect of financial leverage, etc. Their solution in practical management increases the effectiveness of financial management in joint-stock companies.

1- the scheme. The general scheme of financial management

The financial management of a joint-stock company is an integral part of the overall management system, and it, in turn, is a system of rational management of the process of financing the economic activities of joint-stock companies, which involves the movement of financial resources and the formation of financial resources arising from the movement. Based on this, financial management can be characterized as a system of rational and efficient use of capital, as a mechanism for managing the movement of financial resources aimed at increasing the volume of capital, increasing investments and increasing financial resources. Financial management is focused on supporting the normal process of handling financial resources, the effectiveness of which is characterized by the speed of rotation (speed of circulation).

A new difficult stage in the formation of a market economy in the Republic of Uzbekistan has created the need for training in financial management as a science of financial management of a joint-stock company aimed at achieving strategic and tactical goals.

The priority goal of financial management is to maximize the economic efficiency of the property owner. The mechanisms for achieving this goal are an effective dividend and investment policy, the credit policy of the joint-stock company, an adequate policy of liquidity and optimal working capital, maintaining an optimal policy of forming the tax base.

The second goal of financial management complements and clarifies the priority goal. Its essence lies in the organization of effective business cooperation in a joint-stock company with clients and creditors, business entities that serve the business development of this joint-stock company. The mechanism for ensuring the effectiveness of business cooperation is justified by the relations of the parties, the poured funds are fully refunded and controlled for a period, the provision of guarantees, collateral, rent, commodity loans, banking services is the conclusion of an effective scheme for servicing the principal amount of debt.

Our next goal is to ensure the social responsibility of our joint-stock company. The stability of the Joint-Stock Company's business activity creates good prospects for expanding the tax base, increasing employment, increasing demand for means of production, and supporting commercial relations in the interconnection and interaction between market participants inside and outside the country. Special attention is paid to social indicators

affecting economic and financial growth, social planning, investment in human capital, monitoring of potential bankruptcy and business decision-making.

In the process of developing the country's economy, the goals of financial management change.

As mentioned above, the goal of financial management is to maximize profits. However, maximizing the market value of a joint-stock company is not always achieved automatically by maximizing the amount of profit it receives. For example, the resulting high profit can be completely spent on current goals, as a result of which joint-stock companies lose the main source of their financial resources for development. In addition, a high level of profit can be achieved with a high level of financial risk, which may justify a decrease in the market value of joint-stock companies.

Conclusion. In conclusion, it should be noted that the practice of effective management in Uzbekistan is at the stage of development, faces problems related to objective economic difficulties, imperfection of the regulatory framework, insufficient level of training of specialists. The following are considered characteristic of the modern economy:

- privatized joint-stock companies reduce the level of authorized capital;
- high cost of financial resources;
- low investment attractiveness of joint-stock companies;
- underdevelopment of the stock market and financial infrastructure.

Considering the trends and state of changes in the economy of financial management development in the Republic of Uzbekistan allows us to conclude that this area will not only have certain traditions, but also a bright future

References:

1. Салишева, З. И. (2011). Значение упражнений по переводу в процессе обучения узбекскому языку как второму. Вестник Московского государственного лингвистического университета, (630), 154-159.
2. Салишева, З. И. (2019). Ўзбек тили машғулотларида талабалар монологик нутқини ривожлантириш методикасини такомиллаштириш (рус гуруҳларда). Пед. фан. ном.... дис. автореф.
3. Abdukhayotovna, A. K. (2022). THE ROLE OF AUTHENTIC MATERIALS TO DEVELOP PUPILS' COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE IN ENGLISH CLASSES AT ACADEMIC LYCEUMS. Berlin Studies Transnational Journal of Science and Humanities, 2(1.5 Pedagogical sciences).
4. Abduxayotovna, A. X. (2021). AKADEMIK LITSEYLARNING ANIQ YO'NALISHIDA TA'LIM OLAYOTGAN O'QUVCHILARNING KOMMUNIKATIV KOMPETENSIYASINI KOMMUNIKATIV O'YINLAR ORQALI RIVOJLANTIRISH. Современное образование (Узбекистан), (12 (109)), 34-39.
5. Ахмадалиева, Х. (2023). PROFESSINAL TA'LIM YO'NALISHLARIDA TAHSIL OLAYOTGAN O'QUVCHILARNING INGLIZ TILIDAN KOMMUNIKATIV KOMPETENSIYASINI AUTENTIK MATERIALLAR ORQALI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH. Ижтимоий-гуманитар фанларнинг долзарб муаммолари/Актуальные проблемы социально-гуманитарных наук/Actual Problems of Humanities and Social Sciences., 3(8).
6. Musurmanova, A., & Abdukhayotovna, A. K. (2023). THE MOVEMENT OF FOREIGN COUNTRIES IN PROTECTING WOMEN'S RIGHTS AND THE CONTENT OF REFORMS IN OUR COUNTRY. Finland International Scientific Journal of Education, Social Science & Humanities,

11(1), 1074-1080.

7. Abdukhayotovna, A. K. (2022). The Beneficial Angels of Learner-Centered Approach in Prospering Pupils' Communicative Competence in English Classes at Academic Lyceums. *International Journal on Integrated Education*, 5(1), 129-135.
8. Abdukhayotovna, A. K. (2021, June). THE IMPLEMENTING OF MOVIE ACTIVITIES TO DEVELOP PUPILS' COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE IN ENGLISH CLASSES AT ACADEMIC LYCEUMS. In "ONLINE-CONFERENCES" PLATFORM (pp. 102-103).
9. Мойдинова, Э. К. (2019). Дистанционное обучение в современном вузе и использование технологии "e-learning". *NovaInfo. Ru*, (104), 70-72.
10. Мойдинова, Э. К. (2021). РАЗВИТИЕ ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНОЙ КОМПЕТЕНЦИИ БУДУЩИХ УЧИТЕЛЕЙ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА. In СИСТЕМА МЕНЕДЖМЕНТА КАЧЕСТВА В ВУЗЕ: ЗДОРОВЬЕ, ОБРАЗОВАННОСТЬ, КОНКУРЕНТОСПОСОБНОСТЬ (pp. 213-217).
11. Мойдинова, Э. К. (2018). Методы преподавания фразеологических единиц для обогащения словарного запаса. *NovaInfo. Ru*, 1(94), 137-140.
12. Мойдинова, Э. К. (2018). ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ ИКТ В РАЗВИТИИ ПОЗНАВАТЕЛЬНОГО ИНТЕРЕСА ПРИ ИЗУЧЕНИИ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА В НАЧАЛЬНОЙ ШКОЛЕ. ББК 81.411. 2 P89, 225.
13. Kamariddinova, M. E. THE ROLE OF INTERCULTURAL COMMUNICATION IN THE TRAINING FOR FUTURE SPECIALIST OF DIFFERENT FIELDS. *Zbiór artykułów naukowych recenzowanych*, 2, 169.
14. Moydinova, E. (2021). THE ROLE OF MODERN ENGLISH TEACHING TECHNOLOGIES IN THE AGE OF DIGITALIZATION. *Scienceweb academic papers collection*.
15. Moydinova, E. (2022). INGLIZ TILINI O 'QITISHDA INNOVATSION TEXNOLOGIYALARIDAN FOYDALANISHNING IMKONIYATLARI. *Scienceweb academic papers collection*.
16. Moydinova, E. (2022). UNIVERSAL MASOFAVIY TA'LIM SHAROITIDA VEB-KVEST TEXNOLOGIYASIDAN FOYDALANISHNING SAMARADORLIGI. *Scienceweb academic papers collection*.
17. Khidirova, M. A., & Pardayeva, N. G. A. (2021). Translation issues of phraseological units used with animal names from English into Uzbek. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 1(11), 1058-1062.
18. Amirkulovna, K. M., & Jurayevna, E. M. (2023). Analysis of Some Idioms with Negative Meanings in English Language. *Web of Synergy: International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 2(4), 781-784.
19. Amirkulovna, K. M. (2023). Different features and interpretation of phraseological units with zoocomponent in English and Uzbek languages. *Central Asian Journal of Social Sciences and History*, 4(4), 78-83.
20. Khidirova, M. A., & Eshdavlatova, M. J. (2021). Translation problems of proverbs used with the word "money" from English into Uzbek language. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 1(11), 48-52.
21. Khidirova, M., & Pardayeva, N. (2023, May). TYPES OF SEMANTIC RELATIONS IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE, THE NOTION OF SYNONYMY. In *International Conference on Science, Engineering & Technology* (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 67-69).
22. Amirkulovna, K. M., & Jurayevna, E. M. (2022). PHRASEOLOGICAL PROVERBIAL UNITS

USED WITH BODY PARTS FROM ENGLISH INTO UZBEK LANGUAGE. PEDAGOGS jurnali, 12(1), 96-102.

23. Absalamova, G. S. (2022). TA" LIM TIZIMINING JORIY HOLATI VA MAVJUD MUAMMOLAR (M. MONTEN "TAJRIBALAR" ASARI MISOLIDA). Academic research in educational sciences, (Conference), 796-801.

24. Absalamova, G. M. S. (2021). The semantic field of the concept of «family upbringing qualities» in Monten's philosophy and its expression in the Uzbek language. Молодой ученый, (16), 124-125.

25. Sharifovna, A. G. (2021). Michel Monten's Style in His "Essays". Procedia of Social Sciences and Humanities, 1, 364-368.

26. Абсаламова, Г. (2021). Французский мыслитель Мишель Де Монтен о воспитании детей. Общество и инновации, 2(5/S), 217-220.

27. Sharifovna, A. G. (2023, October). MONTEN IJODIDAGI "TAJRIBALAR" ASARIDA FARZAND TARBIYASIDAGI "SALBIY JIHAT" LEKSEMALARINING IJOBIYLIK TOMONLARI. In INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCES WITH HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS (Vol. 1, No. 05.10, pp. 312-314).

28. Khasanov, B. A., & Yarkulova, M. A. (2020). Methods of calculating the cost of products and the possibility of their application in the modern economy of Uzbekistan. Asian Journal of Technology & Management Research [ISSN: 2249-0892] Vol.

29. Яркулова, М. (2023). ОПТИМИЗАЦИЯ ЦЕНООБРАЗОВАНИЯ СТОИМОСТИ УСЛУГИ НА ДАВАЛЬЧЕСКОЙ ОСНОВЕ НА НЕФТЕПЕРЕРАБАТЫВАЮЩИХ ПРЕДПРИЯТИЯХ. Economics and education, 24(2), 26-32.

30. Яркулова, М. (2022). Совершенствование традиционных методов калькулирования себестоимости продукции нефтеперерабатывающих предприятий. MOLIYA VA BANK ISHI, 8(3), 166-170.

31. Yarkulova, M. A., & Safarboeva, F. A. (2022). ADVANTAGES OF INTRODUCING THE ERP SYSTEM AT THE ENTERPRISES OF THE OIL AND GAS COMPLEX OF UZBEKISTAN. Economics and Innovative Technologies, 2022(2), 10.

32. Яркулова, М. А. (2022). ПОСТРОЕНИЕ ЭКОНОМЕТРИЧЕСКОЙ МОДЕЛИ ПРОИЗВОДСТВЕННОЙ СЕБЕСТОИМОСТИ НЕФТЕПЕРЕРАБАТЫВАЮЩЕЙ ОТРАСЛИ.

33. Яркулова, М. А. ТРАНСФОРМАЦИЯ МЕТОДОВ КАЛЬКУЛИРОВАНИЯ СЕБЕСТОИМОСТИ ПРОДУКЦИИ НЕФТЕПЕРЕРАБАТЫВАЮЩИХ ПРЕДПРИЯТИЙ НА МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЕ СТАНДАРТЫ БУХГАЛТЕРСКОГО УЧЕТА.

34. Abdiraimov, S. (2023). Theoretical and Methodological Basis of Assessment of Reading Comprehension in Mother Tongue Education. Periodica Journal of Modern Philosophy, Social Sciences and Humanities, 18, 155-168.

35. ABDIRAIMOV, S. O 'ZBEKISTON MILLIY UNIVERSITETI XABARLARI, 2021,[1/4] ISSN 2181-7324.

36. ABDIRAIMOV, S. TASK METHODOLOGY USED IN ASSESSMENT OF READING SKILLS. Social sciences.